

MIMS 2.2.5.2¹ - The Five “forces” that Influence Life

Using the Wuxing (5 Element) and “Big G” diagram to analyze the
locations of Karma, Luck, Fate, Destiny, and Chaos

August 2022

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ABSTRACT

The author discusses the internal mystery and self-consistency of the Five Forces + “Big G” diagram through the Diagrammatica found in the Wuxingming Tu. These cooperational, even polar, reflections of metaphysical philosophae suggest new areas for human toil and research, and provide answers for some of life’s toughest mysteries, with an almost brutally honest (tonally) retrospection based on facts and circumstances. This paper is not for those that are offended by facts and painful reminders of historical facts. Suggested pre-reading: POS Theory and Change Theory, as well as various MIMS studies linked throughout.

Key Words: MIMS - Religion - STEMM - Changes - Economics - Wisdom - Numerology - SPACERS

¹ Potentially MIMS 4.02; but as much as little will the author rely on religion’s authority so much as its opinions and sayings. A later crossover might be useful based on this Change Theory sub-subject.

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The Diagrammatic Description

Figure 1 - the Five "Forces" of Life (The "wuxingmingtu"²)

² 五性命图, lit: 5 Nature/Quality Bright/Destiny Diagram; Wuxing is a homonym also for the five phases.

Figure 2 - The Big G³ “regions” in comparison to the powers and ‘fibonacci’ (Chinese) encoding; note the hidden Judeo-Christian alignments which confirm the MIMS diagram is global and diffuse, not localized, and may suggest non-locality (Universality)

Meaning & Mapping

The subtle meanings and overt religious and common meanings for each of these “forces” of life, or Regions, or ‘domains’ of influence in our lives, and in physics, are not very well defined, in all cases. Take, for example Karma:

1. “Law of Sowing and Reaping”
2. “Newton’s 1st Law”

³

http://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

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3. "What goes around, comes around"
4. "The Golden Rule"
5. "Sin"
6. "What goes up, must come down"
7. Generational curses (in some cases 4, some cases 7 generations which the 'Lord' exacts his vengeance upon)
8. Hindu Karma, which is based in all actions
9. Etc.

Karma

Any one culture, group, scientific cadre, journal, etc. have a different meaning for it. What is interesting is the Buddha had perhaps the most comprehensive definition in the "Lotus Sutra"⁴ which included the linear *and nonlinear* dynamics of Causality, which is surely an "Ark of the Covenant" level of 'Pandora's Box'. OR rather: a black box equation for which we have no basis, and probably have no right or business knowing the full equation, for as surely as we did we would undo ourselves. Even the pursuit of it probably should be verboten! Nevertheless, Quantum physicists have spent the last 30 years arguing whether any of these simultaneous 'forces' or Domains/Regions have a true or great impact on Conservation and Causality, and more or less, if we can even disregard Causality. Of course, we cannot, for it is the "King of Laws" occupying the Heaven position, and Fire position (Spirit), and as surely as we tried to upend it, we should perish, even as our proverbial archetypes of Atlantis and Krypton.

The Buddha spoke it⁵ (in Mahayana tradition) as this:

"Sho i shoho, nyo ze so, sho, tai, riki, sa, en, in, ka, ho, honmak kukyo to" (Japanese)
It has been called the 12-linked Chain of Causation⁶ in Hinayana and Theravada (Pali Canon), but the right translations as per Watson are:

"The Buddha's understanding can only be shared between Buddhas, and this reality consists of:

1. *Appearance*
2. *Nature*
3. *Entity*
4. *Power*
5. *Influence*
6. *Inherent Cause*
7. *Relation*
8. ***Latent Effect***
9. *Manifest Effect*
10. *Consistency*
11. *From beginning to end*

⁴

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BwoOz_mUBUfuR3luWkZDbjFPZG8/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-E0i3HUaUZuvKvNjXPUbUdA

⁵ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bM8pa3JYQiygmghl88gHyxE8eCOLLxTs-/view?usp=sharing>

⁶ <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/chain-causation>

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"Stop, stop!... if I speak of [the Lotus Sutra] the heavenly and human beings through the worlds will be astonished and doubtful. The monks who are overbearingly arrogant will fall into a great pit."⁷

The key to understanding why this is superior to a Cartesian-Newtonian⁸ version is simple, it implies **storage** in an aether/akashic form (ruled by Physics' or *P* power's Law of Conservation) of the input data, and the re-emergence as an output data. This is most commonly called stimulus-response in the biological and chemistry studies associated with the Law of Evolution:Flux (wind trigram, first augural motion out of Causality).

L.U.C.K.

As for 'Lady Luck' and her fickle attitudes of fortune and misfortune, which may or may not in reality be related to the stars, planets, their influences, the angels, yada yada, the best mimsical recreation has been labeled as it is here: "Living Under Correct Knowledge."

Bear in mind that knowledge is gnosis⁹, in the original Greek, and implies some discussion of the Logos¹⁰, which is an ineffable discussion not for this paper. But we will push forward a bit into describing how the relationships of the diagram describe this improvement in the MIMS and its apparent successes, later. Suffice it to say: whatever 'fengshui'¹¹ or money, or other MIMS' attempts to attract the fortunes of Lady Luck, they appear to be less capable than Aether (*A* power) and good Karma, over the short and long term, respectively. This implies some connection to the *F* power's rules of Charge, and yet outside of epigenetics (and telomeres), we do not know how the action of electrifying DNA via breathing works. There is some evidence for transmutation in a particle acceleration environment inside the Benzene ring dominated structures of the DNA molecule. Also, with all the coiling, there is a sufficient amount of storage of current via induction, and charge via capacitance. Exercise, especially forms of calisthenics (like yoga, Taijiquan¹², Bagua Zhang, pilates, egoscue, etc.) appear to have serious benefits in these regards, and do appear to positively affect fortunes in a much more predictable and peer-accepted (and socioculturally accepted) manner than methods of fengshui and superstitious activities, such as voodoo dolls, golden cats that wave placed in corners, dowsing, chanting, etc. In short, since the "Big G" powers are based on the PEMF¹³ and guided by the interaction of the 0, 1, and 8 laws, then we should expect that any MIMS that conforms closer to

⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/Lotus-Sutra-Burton-Watson/dp/0231081618/>

⁸ "for every action (force) in nature there is an equal and opposite reaction."

<https://www1.grc.nasa.gov/beginners-guide-to-aeronautics/newtons-laws-of-motion/>

⁹ "Knowledge of spiritual mysteries"

¹⁰ "the Word of God, or principle of divine reason and creative order, identified in the Gospel of John with the second person of the Trinity incarnate in Jesus Christ."

¹¹ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl> pp.93 on

¹²

https://www.academia.edu/39776252/Ancient_Origins_of_Taijiquan_Do_plasmaglyphics_belie_a_more_ancient_origin_of_the_internal_martial_art_of_Taijiquan_An_EPEMC_Analysis

¹³ Plasma-electromagnetic Force

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physical laws and especially the Force (F power) will be more effective in this electrification of DNA, and this may combine with gnosis (a form of L power) to generate better Luck.

Fate

The determinant state of matter is a subject of very hot dispute in quantum and other physics circles. Einstein famously said, “God does not play dice with the Universe” to which Bohr retorted, “Einstein, please stop telling God what to do.”

Then there is this quip, “Remember: if it disagrees with experiment, it’s wrong.”¹⁴

That’s why anyone saying light is a particle, is wrong. Anyone saying it is a wave, is wrong. As a circuit, light is able to behave as a wave or particle and is modeled as a virtual particle, which we call a photon.¹⁵

This is to say that in the case of determinism¹⁶, some things are determinant, and some are not. The sum of all linear summations of events has a very high predictable outcome. But not completely so. Furthermore, the attempt to remove determinism has been thwarted both with logic and experiment. The summary of the attempts is that there is an indication that we can only know Fate once the events are “dead” (determined), and then the summation is Fate. This is in stark contrast to Destiny¹⁷, which is a revealed moment-to-moment chain of events that is not ceased but in motion. Between these lies Chaos.

CHAOS

The Hundun is a place of ‘undifferentiated chaos’ which is to say, an idea that the average density of the entropy is 100%, which for us is 100% order. That maintains a perfect equilibrium of Potential in our Void (counterspace), which enables a Spongy Counterspatial (SCS) absorption of our energy and entropy, and return of a trickle of particulate and aetheric data (Aether-plasma, baryonic and neutrino dust, etc.) This is all part of the Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis¹⁸ discussion of “Two Way Entropy” (Dual Direction Entropy)¹⁹, which is not for this paper. But in this section we must describe the chaos of events, the chaos of particulate chemistry and solar chemistry, nuclear fission and fusion, and other high energy ultra hot or ultracold physical events, etc., as well as the randomness in the power of Numbers (N

¹⁴ Feynman <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UD6VsPz6Bf8>

¹⁵ https://www.academia.edu/72712372/OpEd_Light_photons_Cannot_Possibly_be_a_Real_Particle

¹⁶ “Noun PHILOSOPHY

1. *the doctrine that all events, including human action, are ultimately determined by causes external to the will. Some philosophers have taken determinism to imply that individual human beings have no free will and cannot be held morally responsible for their actions.”*

¹⁷ Recommended reading: Xingming Guizhi

https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BwoOz_mUBUfuNmlkNmcyNmpnYm8/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0_wG3dpQERBLO_OWMdys3X4w

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

¹⁹

https://www.academia.edu/37439506/Magnetic_Universe_Theory_A_Top_Down_Review_of_Phases_of_Magnetic_Theory_Development_with_accompanying_historiography_and_comparison_with_Unified_Aether_Field_Theories_including_EPEMC

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power), as well as infinity and eternity, which all fall into the C region or domain of CHAOS. In short “you just never know.” It is a region that haunts the religious and scientific alike and confounds all attempts at totalitarian hegemony over life.

Destiny

As mentioned before the *D* region consists of an *unfolding*, ‘actionless’, phase of the wuxing or Dao (Tao), where the flux is transitioning from unification into defacto polarization, and where Causality’s Karma (*K* region) is unfolding into the two paths people take as in good lives or bad. Now the particular interaction where Karma enables bad people to do good, or to live, and to ‘get away with murder’ is actually an interaction of Causality with Conservation, or the *K* and *F* regions. We all know the Fate of Hitler, may he and other despots burn forever! However, what boggles us is that “no good deed goes unpunished” (especially when you “go out of your Way”), and that “good guys finish last,” and well frankly, children *do* die of cancer and heart maladies. It seems **evil** to us, but clearly there is a Universal Function maintained by the *P* power in the 8 Laws. “What the Heck” is the common reply and “why God, Why?!” to natural disasters, cheating spouses, dead kids, and much else.

The Destiny domain is where our ego (Liver/Wood phase) drives us to *act*, and the Law of Rotation active in CHAOS provides new opportunities at all times for us to mimsically chase, attach, obtain, etc.

The author was at once rejected and depressed one night and asked out the next day, “you just never know.” Right? This domain is itself polar, and therefore there is a separate type of unfolding for women and for men. The “man rules” exist because male worlds are violent, and the “3 obediences”²⁰ for women (from Buddhism) are not a result of “the Patriarchy” so much as inborn aspects of the polar compliment to the yang gender. It isn’t a ‘conspiracy’, it is a natural biological enfolding.

How this affects everyone’s dualistic experience is extremely abstruse and ungratifying, because the polar relation to Wood is Earth (Luck), and the polar relation to Polarity is Relativity (water, as in Chaos). Therefore, there is a simultaneous belief in free will and freedom to chase one’s Destiny but a constant feeling of oppression, obstruction, difficulty, and pitfalls (all Changes according to the Chinese), and more to the point, one often compares oneself, unfairly, to others. “The grass is always greener on the other side,” plagues people, and their feelings of isolation, failure, etc. are bad for psychology, and good for biology, driving sexual deviancy and lack of planned pregnancies, which is Mother Nature’s way to use chaos to improve genetic pools! What else is ungratifying is that as each polar gender attempts to be more like the other they lose their own selves and become less fulfilled, and suicides are often the results. If one is not able to be the ‘ideal’ male or female, it often drives people (especially now with the Socialist pathogen flitting about, mingling with Coronavirus mRNA manipulations), to doubt their identities, sexually or spiritually, etc. This creates a huge de facto presence in psychiatric data of general unhappiness. This increases CHAOS’ influence on society as people enact aberrant (or less normal) behaviors in attempts to self-medicate and adjust, etc.) to the issues everywhere.

²⁰ To the father, the husband, and then to the son; self-appointed shackles.

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Combine this with solar mediated Climate Change²¹ (due to charge rearrangements in the Local Chimney or other SSEC-GEC²² axial dynamism), and magnetospheric alterations, which would alter psychological stimulus-response behaviors, well you have the chance for many ego-driven self-destruction moments in life.

Destiny is rarely reached, according to the Chinese concept of full perfection, “gong”²³. One may practice and practice, and not yet achieve, because of the other four forces, or the God-Source may intervene. “Heaven only knows” and “Heaven forbid” tend to indicate some challenge to our assumptions that we are in charge of our lives. And deep down, we also know that “living only for the moment/today” is bad for us, physically and psychologically. We even teach in religions worldwide it can send you to Hell, though we have no data on this at all. When people come back from NDE²⁴, mostly they explain a Void or a Heaven-like experience. But maybe a Lake of Fire experience would be good for people, but so far Buddhism’s concept of a Living Hell (samsara) appears to be the most cogent, mimsically useful, and realistic. Take the landscapes of WW1 and the holocaust of WW2 which are perfect examples of both the anti-MIMS of war and of a living Hellscape. Again: another paper.

Diagrammatica

Short for Diagrammic Mathematica, we are here interested in the mimsy **stemming** from the five-phase and six-division (not heavily in this paper) interactions between the five regions and the G power. These interactions are related to the N power’s daethereal influences, as well as the Law of Conservation, both of which occupy the same general region of the Birkeland Superweb. See the following diagram for comparison:

²¹

https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

²² “Magnetic Universe” Table 17

²³ 工 meaning skill; note it is a cosmic pole motif/plasmaglyphic. Meaning Thunderbolt of the One above.

²⁴ Near Death Experience

Figure 3 - The relative Birkeland positions of the Law of Conservation and Power of Numbers, based on the “eye of Horus/Odin” orientation, and rotational keys provided by the Allegewi/Hopewell. Credit: NASA/Author

This last diagrammatica is probably less important than the coherence of the PEMF flow through the once representative of the *L* power/king (as Marduk²⁵ or Jehovah/Jove). But the PEMF in Jupiter’s core and plasmasphere is not the subject of this paper, this is a philosophy paper. But what intrigues us is that there **are** these powers and domains (or regions) of influence, and they are mappable, and useful, intrinsically and extrinsically. Intrinsically, there is a self-consistency that develops in cross comparison of myths, religions, and even sciences (Chinese versus Anglo-European²⁶). Extrinsically, when the unrelated subjects become related, there are opportunities to look at how Causality breaks into various methods of expression all because of the types of forces influencing it.

Let’s look for a couple of the interactions in these dynamics:

❖ Karma → L.U.C.K.

- Living under correct Knowledge is what the Buddha called “Right Living” and part of the Noble Eightfold Path
 - Right Understanding, Right Thought, Right Speech, Right Action, Right Livelihood, Right Effort, Right Mindfulness and Right Concentration²⁷
 - Remember that the word for ‘right’ and ‘correct’ share the plasmaglyphics with ‘upright’ and ‘righteous’ and contain the roots of the Cosmic Pole motif!
- The issue is that generally speaking, “doing the right thing” is considered “good luck” or “good karma” already, and that to “Know the good is to do the good,” (Aristotle). Therefore, one is supposed to be happy with doing good without any reward or need to brag, or it is a false action.
- This leads, inevitably to the concept of “yoga of Action”²⁸ which contains the elements of wu-wei where the Bhagavan subconsciously does the Will of God (Brahma-Atman) by adhering to “dharma” (thus Dharma and Karma crossover), and elements of not mere spontaneity but literal Godliness, which Christians call “Holiness.”
 - Discussions of Holiness versus moral and ethical living have been compiled elsewhere²⁹
 - God is Holy, all the time.

²⁵ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm> Tablets 4 and 5

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/37784032/Chinese_Natural_Philosophy_Physics_in_EPEMC

²⁷ <https://www.pbs.org/edens/thailand/buddhism.htm>

²⁸ <https://www.holy-bhagavad-gita.org/index>

²⁹ https://www.academia.edu/66889409/MIMS_4_01_Morality_as_a_Simulation_of_Holiness

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- Dharma, or “God’s Plan” (as christians know it), appears to be also about the Changes, and accepting these “with grace” is to attract more of “God’s Grace.” Thus, Yeshua said, “The meek shall inherit the Earth”³⁰
 - This form of Fortune, therefore, can be said to be a reward for “sinless” behavior, since karma comes from good and bad actions alike. So we have reminders and old wive’s wisdom:
 - “An apple a day keeps the doctor away”
 - “A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush”
 - “No point crying over spilled milk.”
 - “Never bite the hand that feeds you.”
 - Etc.
 - Whereas the nonlinear aspects of luck, such as misfortune and bad luck appear to be applied socially only to good people, while misfortune and bad luck for criminals and miscreants is seen as “just desserts” or a reward for awful living. This might be right, or completely wrong and pure bunkish theological superstition. Given most good families kids become good people who succeed in reproducing and holding jobs, and not being criminals, etc., despite Universal sin, supports the former over the latter. But, again, without Data... how would we really know? We need the Change Theory to be applied and codified!
- ❖ Karma → Fate
- The *K* region controlling the *F* region appears to be a matter of good or bad living. Evil people go to Hell, is basically Universally accepted, except by atheists, who can - according to this and their own philosophies, be ignored.
 - But do all good people or righteous people go to Heaven? There is **not** Universal agreement on this, even within the faiths, and even between people of similar faiths. Ranging from the magic water “Baptists” to “only by the Roman emperor’s special power” Catholics, to the “you’re all going to get scrubbed in 7 Hells” Tibetans to “Warriors get a special Heaven” Vikings... well there really just is no agreement as to the rewards for “good karma” beyond the fortunes of feeling and obvious career benefits of the Eightfold Path, as applied to kama (householder life).
 - People do seem to agree that religious “saints” all go to Heaven, male or female, but not whether or not women can become enlightened without being male (yang)! There is some evidence to suggest that few men can make it to Heaven, but not a lot of evidence women are desired there, nor that they *cannot* make it there. Most people think their grandma made it to Heaven, even if unbeknownst to them she was a literal or figurative whore. The Bible talks much of the “Strange Woman,” and her paths to Hell (presumably through her crotch!), but realistically, if she has lots of children, who among them will claim she was a devil woman? But obviously, there are several “white witch” and “medusa” traditions worldwide that condemn women, despite the fact that it is men who conduct warfare and

³⁰ Matthew 5:5 Not to be confused with the weak. The meek have a humble and patient bearing, and are not proud or demanding, nor do they shirk from even violent responsibilities. But they do not seek problems and are not “forward” (King James Bible translation).

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genocides! So again, the data is not strong, and the social conventions or “common sense” is not scientific in this regard. Sexism seems to be the overriding punishment since “all decent ‘enough’ women go to Heaven.”³¹

- More usefully, descriptions of the Fate of men and women in their living Life and not their afterlife is probably helpful to finding mimsical evidence and practical use to this control axis.

❖ L.U.C.K. → Fate

- How your good or bad luck - your fortunes - lead to Fate seems so simple to talk about. But realistically, what do we know about it? “He died young, must have been his bad luck to eat that piece of meat that killed him” is a glib way of dismissing a powerful force in one’s life. Perhaps it is too frustrating or confounding to put much time, and especially money, let alone strong philosophy into it. We focus on teaching kids how to have good karma and reduce sin, hoping this will charge them with Heaven’s Aether, and “grace” and they will just “have an angel on their shoulders”
- But what if angels are only attracted by success, and sent away by failure?
- Yeshua said, *“For whoever has, to him more will be given; and whoever does not have, even what he has will be taken away from him”*³²
 - This is an inherently nonlinear statement, and irrational.
- It may very well be that there is much more to say on the matter, but suffice it for now: people expect that bad fortune “comes in threes” and just expect that “some days you should have just stayed in bed”³³ ... and one of these types of days might claim your life. And there is nothing you can do about it (apparently?)

❖ L.U.C.K. → CHAOS

- However, there is a **lot** believed and said (in religion, mostly) about how good fortunes, and specifically L.U.C.K. (mostly Right Living) can do to protect you from the “bogeyman” of chaos. Most particularly “the Grim Reaper.”
 - This is fascinating when one considers the plasmaglyphics of the scythe in Saturn³⁴, and Odin’s stories of reaping giants, and mortals, etc.
- The main things said are that you will have the protection of various anti-bogeymen:
 - Ancestors
 - Guardian angels
 - House spirits
 - Angels of Heaven
 - Saints
 - Forest spirits
 - Sprites and other natural guides
- OR if you are a naughty child, you will have the dangers of various bogeymen:

³¹ Fact is there are more women, and based on a lot of present activities, we can reasonably guess that if there is a Hell, it is mostly populated with women, % wise.

³² Mark 4:25

³³ Bugs Bunny

³⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oophJNIP-fk>

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- Forest witches
- Warlocks
- Leprechauns
- Evil spirits
- Enchanted elves
- Devils and daemons
- Satan himself
- Kidnappers and other evil men
 - Interestingly women eat them, while men murder children; rarely is sexual rape and assault mentioned, when in fact we know this is the gravest danger within isolated families and communities, even with modern computerization and cameras on phones.
- The force of CHAOS is said to be completely out of our control, but perhaps if we attract Lady Luck, we can mitigate it, and “have an angel on our shoulders.”
 - Might be true, might be bunk. We honestly have no real data, even though we have “beyond a plethora” of anecdotal evidence.
 - It seems like common sense.

❖ Fate → CHAOS

- Fate generating chaotic domains of influence in our lives appears to be a statement about the *A* power and Heaven in general. It has a tight relationship with Karma, but for this let us focus on the Metal generating Water function. Literally, the Chinese saw that minerals attract dew, and the concept of the Waters (from the waters) being associated with black in color suggests that the White and Black relationship is itself here. Meaning Order and Chaos, respectively. Pure Order is the White Space and vice versa is also true. This is a hard dichotomy that must exist to have the “rainbow of gray” demanded of Conservation by Relativity.
- Nevertheless, it seems that only *sometimes* does one’s Fate mean chaos will take one’s life. More truthfully, **all life** experiences Chaos. Thus the saying, “Expect the unexpected.”
- There is probably more to say, relating the electric flux of Metal (as in nerves) with the void of Water (as in essence or endocrine system), but is it worth the time?
 - The probable flow of this subcurrent should be in MIMS 1.X.X.1+ as a discussion of the behaviors of water, especially Pollack’s EZ Water, with the Aether, and PEMF in general (such as water bridges, etc.)

❖ Fate → Destiny

- How Fate controls Destiny should seem obvious. If one is fated, one achieves Destiny, or even lives beyond it. If one is not fated, one is robbed. Let’s use some real-life examples:

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- Bruce Lee is a man whose Destiny was clearly robbed by his Fate; and this relates to his drug use³⁵ and failure to protect his excellent Bazi alignment³⁶ from the alchemical mistake of “burning the Medicine” (Dan)³⁷
- Michael Jordan achieved his Destiny publicly, and continues to achieve more and more... maybe more than any man ever... but few think about him beyond his 1998 crescendo shot. It’s as if he publicly died. And he prefers to no longer be “God on the basketball court” (according to Larry Bird).
- Robin Williams achieved his Destiny, and then turned to darkness, and killed himself³⁸, but is forgiven by the public who only remembers the happy side of him, even though he reached the fate in the Huangdi neijing³⁹ for “fire types” and died young.
- Michael Jackson was killed by chaos (of iatrogenic drugs⁴⁰), just as Bruce Lee, but most think he achieved his best work already and was guilty of grave sins⁴¹. He was, legally speaking, innocent. Many lamented his loss, but some appeared relieved that a pedophile was dead. Nevertheless, “it is what it is” seemed to be the general take on his death.
- David Carradine died a most dishonorable and embarrassing death⁴², ironically given his fake persona as a kungfu master (stolen from Bruce Lee⁴³). He accidentally suicided while masturbating, and became a joke. His Fate however came *well after* his Destiny, and so most ignore his death and review his life and work favorably, even though he was reputed to be quite an egomaniac.
- Kobe Bryant’s fate was written even in cartoon form⁴⁴ (as a bizarre anti-MIMS?) well ahead, and he had already achieved his Destiny... but many felt nevertheless very sad because his Fate also robbed others of their Destiny. Does this suggest that one can spread bad fortune, choice-karma, and even Fate onto others? That is a frightening prospect for Chaos, since it is thus far (without conspiracy) considered chaos and “bad luck” which enabled his Fate to rob his Destiny, or at least “wrap it up too early.” (He had many things to live for and do, and all agree his daughter and others’ deaths were extra tragic⁴⁵).

³⁵ <https://blackbeltmag.com/bruce-lee-drug-use>

³⁶ <https://joeyyap.com/tutorial/tutorial-details.asp?tid=532>

³⁷ See “The Threefold Sciences” section on the Elixir and Field plasmaglyphics and etymology

³⁸ <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/robin-williams-mental-health-zak-son>

³⁹ https://www.academia.edu/43951590/Huang_Di_Nei_Jing_Su_Wen

⁴⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Death_of_Michael_Jackson

⁴¹

<http://www.npr.org/2019/03/05/699995484/michael-jackson-a-quarter-century-of-sexual-abuse-allegations>

⁴²

<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-carradine/david-carradine-died-of-asphyxiation-pathologist-idUSTRE5610CD20090702>

⁴³ <https://screenrant.com/kung-fu-show-cw-bruce-lee-connection-explained/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.mirror.co.uk/news/us-news/kobe-bryant-helicopter-crash-death-21370321>

⁴⁵ His legal innocence in the rape charge is mostly accepted, as compared to Jackson’s. However, it is possible that is part of his data stream. Compare this with Mike Tyson’s defacto guilty charge, but general

❖ CHAOS → Destiny

- How chaotic forces of life, particularly the water-void (essential) create one's opportunities for Destiny is a subject of deep Taoist reflection. While Lieh-tzu (Liezi) took the extreme drunken position that there is **nothing you can do** to avoid your Fate⁴⁶, most of the Taoists seem to have a more Te-based idea⁴⁷. Slow, repeated efforts of life discipline (often gongfu or other 'gentlemen's ways') leads to "moral force" which becomes "inner force" and can be "lodged in the chest." This zong Qi "cleans the heart"⁴⁸ (chakra), meaning a good (negative) charge forces out the bad (positive) charge, helping attract MORE aether (spirit Qi), leading to Zheng Qi, and this casts out Bing or Xie Qi (diseases and evils, respectively).
- Moreover, that destiny is literally an unfolding, it could be said that the entire axis here is a direct representation of the PPPC:
 - Potentiality
 - Possibility
 - Probability
 - Cloud
- What is affecting the final outcome of the particle beam is not merely magnetic and electric fields, and polarizations, but also actual chaotic "jiggle" or randomness, informed from the *N* power or *F* region. So, again the black box of nonlinear dynamical causation is keeping us from understanding how to know the future **precisely**, but we can project it fairly **accurately**. This is a nuisance, but we conjecture in this philosophy that if the MIMS is 'good' and 'godly' and 'scientific' or 'nature guided' then it stands a better and better chance, with

50/50 doubt in the public of his actual guilt (and his maintenance of innocence) and you get a really interesting comparison. How does a man of violence with guilty rape charge live and become nearly worshipped, even with communist tattoos and public displays of erratic behaviors (as well as poetic license)? And how does a man of innocent rape charge get killed "too young" in the flower of life? Chaos, like the death of Rocky Marciano, appears to be the common denominator, and **not sin**. Tyson's life is almost a defiance of "There is a way that seemeth right to a man, but leadeth to death." Then again: what do we know, as a public observer?

⁴⁶ <https://terebess.hu/english/tao/Lieh-tzu-Eva-Wong.pdf>

⁴⁷ <https://www.amazon.com/Original-Tao-Foundations-Mysticism-Translations/dp/0231115652>

⁴⁸ "The vital essence (Jing) of all things:

It is this that brings them to life.

When stored within the chests of human beings,

We call them sages.

Just let a balanced and aligned breathing fill your chest

And it will swirl and blend within your mind,

This confers longevity.

When joy and anger are not limited,

You should make a plan to limit them.

Just let a balanced and aligned breathing fill your chest.

For people who have attained the Way

It permeates their pores and saturates their hair.

Within their chest, they remain unvanquished."

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concentration of consciousness, of producing the outcome expected. Of improving life and the environment. This is the meaning of xingming⁴⁹ defacto. It is the entire purpose of 'fengshui' and other luck-based pursuits... to promote Life and Destiny.

❖ CHAOS → Karma

- CHAOS controlling Karma is a subject of much irritation. On the first hand, asking a minister "why did God allow XYZ?" never leads to a satisfactory answer, only platitudes.
- Secondly, the inherent feeling of powerlessness leads to many sayings, wisdoms, and aphorisms that are irrational or flat-out contradictory, and only work as wisdom when applied with wisely observed context.
- Few people are wise.
- So to most people this solution set sounds "like bullshit."
- This causes many good people to abandon God for feeling abandoned by God.
- Even though we never know the entire nonlinear equation (or what happened and why to that loved one we lost, etc.)
- It's a motif of writing which never gets old because it is so common
- But if one's goodness or badness controlled all Causality, by itself, we'd be in a perpetual state of "beatings which will continue until morale improves."
- In fact, there is a wide tolerance for your POS behavior⁵⁰ by Heaven, which the A power is related via water to CHAOS (again a black and white relationship).
- It took a long time for George Floyd's bad behaviors to catch up to him, then he died exactly as one would expect⁵¹. Suicide by cop is a common motif. Ironically it was still unacceptable to us as people, but a fact-based observation of his life defies this surmise and makes the whole situation tragic.
 - It also spread into the Destiny and Karma of an entire nation and even the world, because it was used by wider powers as a planned powder keg
 - Heaven's only response, that we can measure and point to, was to zap his mural in the face with lightning⁵². Presumably for being buried as a moral king (in a gold coffin⁵³) despite living as a miscreant and dying on drugs.
 - The grander meaning for "right living" and more to the point (for naughty people and POS) is puzzling, because some have lived very long lives on drugs or being pedophiles, etc.
 - Therefore, how Chaos chose this moment to control Karma, but not others, only deepens the great mystery of the Law of Causality (sowing and reaping). See: Buddha's prescriptions above.

⁴⁹ Life & Destiny (as objects to acquire)

⁵⁰ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

⁵¹ Drugs, pimping, alcohol, fighting cops, robbery, etc.

⁵² <https://fox8.com/news/photos-lightning-destroys-george-floyd-mural-in-ohio/>

⁵³

<https://www.quora.com/Why-was-George-Floyd-canonized-and-buried-in-a-gold-casket-surrounded-by-weeping-celebrities-and-US-state-officials-who-seemed-all-overwhelmed-with-grief-by-his-death>

❖ Destiny → Karma

- The way that Destiny generates Karma seems, again, very obvious. Most say it has to do with a “positive attitude” or “negative” (or cynical) one. Or that it is a matter of “effort” and “mind over matter.”
- Destiny - or chasing one’s inner “uncarved block”⁵⁴ appears to be itself considered the most positive form of karma, save for accepting Salvation of the Lord.
- However, it is precisely what the Buddha (and Taoists) often advised against.
- Precisely because the ego, or “I-sense”, leads to so many destructive behaviors, as is well written about, and supplied with ample historical examples.
 - This sort of supports the ideas about the Atman written of earlier
 - Or that the Chinese are right and since “everyone is a thief” then one needs to accept God’s love and just live your life... because you are going to become a “screw up” or even a POS (defacto or ‘to someone else’)
- However, no one has proved either of these circumstances:
 - That pursuing your anti-Destiny, whatever that is, produces bad Karma
 - Or that you can eliminate Karma by not pursuing your Destiny
- Also, no one has been capable to prove that not pursuing your Destiny or pursuing your anti-Destiny would itself not be your Destiny!
- All MIMS in this regard seem to indicate that interfering with your Karma and Fate is a fool’s errand; but not even a percent of people will do this. Almost all will chase Destiny!

❖ Destiny → L.U.C.K.

- The control that Destiny has over one’s fortunes appears to be a matter of the Force controlling Relativity.
 - We know now that General Relativity, like Special Relativity, should be understood through the whole Force, not the special conditions of gravity!
- This means that if one achieves Destiny, one is “fortunate” (unless that Destiny be considered misfortune!)
- And conversely if one fails to achieve Destiny, then one is unfortunate. And you can then blame Fate and Karma and Chaos and simply sigh and say “Ke xi ah” (what a shame!)
- There is no data to prove this, it is a feeling that people have. It might be completely ridiculous, and certainly trusting in the relative judgments of others is incredibly ill-advised and flawed.
- But it is only through the lens of others’ views that we develop a sense of a mimsical application, on a micro or macro scale.
- And it is only through the Numbers and Aether - the daethereal evidence - that we gather any remote data on ideas such as Manifest Destiny⁵⁵. America was incredibly fortunate geographically and geologically, but its history has been

⁵⁴ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pu_\(Taoism\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pu_(Taoism))

⁵⁵ <https://www.ushistory.org/us/29.asp>

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mired in blood. Now Lady Luck appears to turn on the United States and the world that is hooked (dangerously) into her via economics (wood-metal)

- We honestly have no clue how to “right the ship” or “turn this around” and go from bad luck back to good luck; and the nonlinear equations of Fatal-causality are going to inform Karma, and the outcomes do not, at present, appear pretty.
 - Shorters (put options etc.) beware: no one can tell the precise future, as has been noted many times above.
 - Dr. M. Burry, who was once successful, has himself shorted the US bond market, and he feels confident in his analysis
 - The author agrees with Burry, but also hopes his crypto plays pan out.
 - Note that bitcoin as a hedge to the dollar has been disproven, and it rises via deflation, not inflation!

❖ Karma, Fate, and Destiny

- When it comes to the classic “dosha” (triple) arrangements, of the five phases, it is always a generalized context. The isotopic and isotropic idiosyncrasies are too incalculable, especially considering the yin-yang of “what’s missing” since 5-3=2.
- Nevertheless, we will try to describe these doshas; starting with the most Heavenly of them. This dosha we can rightfully call “getting what you deserve” or ... in some cases ... what you earn. Just as the author was about to write this, a headline came through on the daethereal supercomputer god (his phone):
 - “US Marshals track down man wanted for torturing his ex-girlfriend only to find suspect riddled with bullets.”⁵⁶
 - “You live by the sword, you die by the sword”⁵⁷ is the aphorism that comes to mind, but all people good and evil will agree, this POS “got what he deserved.”
 - Technically we don’t know this, and his guilt is not proved in court, nor are all circumstances known. But no one will be shocked by his fate, given the charges made against him!
- So the issue is, can one alter one’s Fate by pursuing one’s “best Destiny” and being a good person, therefore getting the best karma? Most would say so...
- Yet Yeshua warned that the road to the Kingdom has nothing to do with doing good acts.⁵⁸
- Yet he also healed people of their “sins”⁵⁹ and exhorted them to “go forth and sin no more”⁶⁰ ... so bad acts definitely had something to do with the Kingdom.
 - Seems to be an irrational and asymmetric demonstration
 - Why many are frustrated by Christianity and religions in general
 - More things seem to kill you than save you; and this makes many questions about an anthropomorphic God, or any God.

⁵⁶ <https://www.theblaze.com/news/us-marshals-find-suspected-torturer-riddled-with-bullets>

⁵⁷ Matthew 26:52

⁵⁸ Matthew 6:1, Ephesians 2:8-10 and others

⁵⁹ <https://faithalone.org/journal-articles/jesus-use-of-spittle-in-mark-822-26/>

⁶⁰ <https://redeeminggod.com/go-and-sin-no-more/>

❖ Luck, CHAOS, and Fate

- This dosha appears to be about “it is what it is” and just accepting the Will of God or Tianyi - Heaven’s Will. “What’s gonna be, is gonna be” is the general belief of the fatalist who accepts the chaos and rejoices equally in blessings.
- But the luck aspirant - a Han Solo type archetype - literally rages against the fatalist (Obi-wan-Kenobi archetype) who declares, as Lieh Tzu did, that there is *nothing* you can do.
- They seek to “jiggle” the situation ever in their favor by manipulating the Shi (position), and hoping to coax chaotic randomness to produce “more than their fair share” of fortune in life.
- The fatalist merely replies that this, too, is fated; and some are “just born lucky.”
- Meanwhile others lament not being “fortunate sons” and participating in the life of chaos, struggle, and corruption; and they tend to accept this as a matter of casted Fate
- In the end this dosha - Life’s Blessings⁶¹ - is considered beyond us humans, and merely a matter of random physics. Since the *L* region occupies the same relative position as the *P* power, we can expect that “living under correct knowledge” is all a matter of “doing the right thing, at the right time, and trusting God to work it all out.”

❖ Fate, Destiny, and CHAOS

- This dosha - which most call “the results of one’s attitudes” - is all about what it is not: karma.
 - Specifically the *K* region’s consciousness relationship to the *L* power
- Much work is spent in religion, politics, economics, and technology, attempting to convert chaos’ opportunities into a Destiny worth being fated to have. Almost all of the economics of the world is based on this mimsical formula.
- If you “do certain things, a certain kind of Way (Tao)” then most often, it is said you will “reap a great harvest.”
- The goal of which is to achieve a Destiny that at the end of life leaves what is called a Legacy
 - **Everyone leaves a legacy**, but we only care about this kind of legacy, and we shun evil ones though we should study them obsessively to prevent evils from being repeated!
- However, if a strong data analysis were conducted, Fate probably would show that this formula for success is *flawed, and unrealistic*.
- A great number of chaos’ first opportunities are often said to be temptations from the Devil.
- The rest are often just “exhaust” from better opportunities!
- Some are outright worthless side quests, pipe dreams, and red herrings.
- A few, if we are honest, appear to be world-altering or life-altering pathways to a Legacy

⁶¹ For by sophistry fortunes are blessings and misfortunates, also, are blessings. Indeed, being unfortunate is even blessings, if the unfortunate is a literal lack of karmic involvement in events.

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- Even in stories of Solomon or currently Elon Musk⁶² we see frequent examples of the “curse” of King Midas.
 - Everything turning to gold can kill one’s heart as surely as lusts
 - Mimsical analysis will probably also prove most of the best mimsy of these figures is from early life, while their later years reek of anti-MIMS
 - King David and Thomas Edison come to mind
- In final surmise this dosha is too valuable to set aside, but too risky to suggest serious technological funding and research be encouraged! It will be, anyhow, because the glory of a thing is not in its risks but its rewards, and greed, is after all, a grand natural aphrodisiac and motivator.

❖ CHAOS, Karma, and Luck

- This dosha appears to be about “playing for keeps” and “playing against the odds”, and is the area where we hope flawed but lovable people (like us!) get rewarded despite their flaws.
 - Consider two stories in “Arabian Nights”: Aladdin⁶³ and Mohommed Hight Lazy-bones⁶⁴
- The fortune of “living under correct knowledge” is its own karmic reward *enough* against Chaos’ jaws and the “evil eye.”
- But, in rare instances, the “good man” (or woman) is considered to be extremely fortunate *if* they are lucky at the same time.
- Misfortune, however, is almost Universally - maybe even suspiciously - accepted to be **a matter of bad karma**, and one’s own sins and shitty behavior.
- By that matter, if chaos punishes the evil men, there will be total acceptance of this as God’s “living” Judgment and a crushing, and rightfully so, of said evil men.
- If misfortune punishes an unlucky, and temporarily wicked criminal, it’s tended to be viewed as “exorcising” the karma, meaning “getting it out”
- The Buddha and disciples called it “outflows” and that all of it must be eliminated in this life to avoid it piling up *in the next life*.
 - Others reject this idea in favor of a Hell prescription and Universal warning against bad behaviors, right or wrong (factually speaking).

❖ Destiny, Luck, and CHAOS

- The final dosha, appears to be about “Dreaming”
- “One has to have a dream” they say, but don’t dreams also sometimes become nightmares? A living nightmare might be worse than no dream at all.
- Yet no one who is a good person will tell a child, “don’t dream, be mediocre.”
 - Except the Taoists, apparently; renowned dead-beat dads!
- The use of opportunities and tragedies to seek one’s fortunes and “become a Hero” to fulfill destiny was the subject of the conversation between Cao-Cao (the wood or ego) and Liu Bei, whom Cao had identified as the only other rival/Hero⁶⁵ (the heart or fire)

⁶² <https://www.wsj.com/articles/elon-musk-affair-sergey-brin-wife-divorce-11658674840>

⁶³ <https://etc.usf.edu/lit2go/pdf/passage/3132/the-blue-fairy-book-001-aladdin-and-the-wonderful-lamp.pdf>

⁶⁴ <http://www.isfdb.org/cgi-bin/title.cgi?1863927>

⁶⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xLTwKwgpqE>

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- In essence, only those with the means, knowledge, skill, will, and finally self-made/man-made luck could even hope to achieve the rare pinnacle of becoming Hegemon.
- This archetype is in the Enuma Elish as Marduk declares himself to be both champion and, *in exchange and not philanthropy*, would be King.
 - The demonstration of planet Jupiter's power over Earth and the planets and planetoids, including smashing them up and rearranging them, was further proof of the right to rule, by force. And it had a worldwide impact on war, which suddenly began as we think of it, 7 kya at the start of the Jovian Era at the junction of the Archaic and Megalithic Periods.
- The "Dream" of "having one's cake and eating it, too," appears to be more than just a matter of fortune, though, but of the principle the Chinese said:
 - "Man's efforts are worth three times the blessings of Heaven."
- The author prefers to say, "Strike the iron until it's hot." All the better if it is already hot, and perhaps even if one can "catch lightning in a bottle."
 - And just as importantly, guard away others that can "steal your thunder" meaning take away that magic feeling you have when you are a success.
- It is very, very hard to be a Joe Louis or Solomon or Babe Ruth or Queen Elizabeth or Victoria. There are always jealous, Napoleonic types who wish to get what you have and take it for themselves, again usually by force or cunning - or both.
- Therefore, this is the dosha that not only deserves (earns) the most respect (street cred) for its "school of hard knocks", but actually rewards one in spades while challenging one - daring one - to be skilled enough to keep it.
- But since most people lose the panache by theft, and not by lack of skill
 - And since most situations are unfairly nonlinear and asymmetric
 - And since one has actually earned this respect and "just praises."
- Then... naturally >>the author most recommends daethereal modeling, involvement, and technological (0th Domain) mimsy in this dosha.<<
- It isn't to show favoritism, they are all real doshas in life; but Luck probably needs Aether to actualize the fortunes, and we definitely need cheap, abundant energy for SPACERS. Chaos is the threat of space and life, and Destiny is both worthwhile as a positive pursuit and inevitable as an egoic attachment.
 - "So why fight it?"
 - "Go with the flow."
- This dosha, guided by the Wood-Water-Earth triangle appears to be also the largest health issue, by far - at least in the Western cultures. Therefore, as an ailment of livers, pancreases, and kidney-adrenals is *crushing* the endocrine systems of our people, and they won't stop striving for their Destinies... why not alleviate this?
- Regardless of the STEMMocological Diagrammatica, let's be real: **we need to invest heavily in SPACERS to save ourselves⁶⁶, our children, etc.**, and

⁶⁶ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

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burning 'wood' energy into 'fire' to melt metal is a fool's errand⁶⁷. We cannot through striving with our Destiny to fight our negative Karma and avoid Fate thereby FORCE people to be better.

- We tried this, it's called The Church
- We even scoured their flesh and tortured their sins out, even at Cahokia⁶⁸ as well as the Jesuits
- Good people will try to be better, and bad people will either give up and rot from the inside out, or chase/attain the Left Hand of Tao and become truly Crowleyesque and Machiavellian.
 - So, in other words, you can't change Human Nature.
- What can be done is technological mimsy (and social?) within the *L*, *D*, and *C* regions, looking for mathematical and physical apparati to describe this dosha, and pursue it with "reality mining" and "enrichening" in **high doses and extreme leverage**.⁶⁹
 - Yes, fully aware of the imbalance it will create, and yet, ignored, for the simple fact that the remaining regions, the *F* and *K*, are a) completely controlled by Heaven, and so all aether (*A* power) will be rate-limited as Heaven sees fit and b) uncontrolled by humans even in the least bit, anyhow.
 - Sure, you make karma, but the equation is only understood by buddhas, so why worry about it - unless you intend to be a buddha and eliminate outflows?
 - Which, let's be honest, no one in kama (householder life) or making Karma remotely cares about outflows. If they have bills, sex, kids, jobs, and money, they have no time for the potential nonlinear-daethereal involvement with their karma. The idea of thinking about it even is unrealistic and unappealing.
 - They can simply have their paradigms altered by religion, psychiatry, propaganda, or whatever it takes to make the mimsically ethical, humanistic society which is egalitarian while protecting biological diversity and individuality (a utopia? Or a "city on a hill" motif?)
- The pursuit of the slight differences between CHAOS and the abstruse fractal variants of the *K* domain which contain various eddies and turbulence, too, will lead to understanding some of life's greatest mysteries.
 - Eg. Did the scooter throw my son (whose subjective experience was that of pure chaos) because he did something stupid or wrong (such as not grip tightly, or be distracted for a moment), or as a punishment? And when it threw him, could doing a breakfall really have prevented a wrist break, or was he **fated** to be tested in his journey west, by having to wear a cast? Not to mention the pain of having to get a bone set!

⁶⁷ Worse than the metaphysical, we are actually physically doing this. How functionally retarded!

⁶⁸ <https://www.amazon.com/Gates-Fengtu-translation-chapters-Exploration/dp/1983405701>

⁶⁹ Again, see "The Threefold Sciences"

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- Also the resultant ‘exhaust’ of the *F-K* duality will likely result in intrinsically beneficial discoveries in physics and math, chemistry, and neurobiology that could result in things as strange as turning retarded children into geniuses⁷⁰, or turning criminals into saintly heroes (not heroes with hundreds of murders!), or turning villains into healers (like St. Paul, whose only mimsy was prayer and writing, and is reputed to have been converted by God Himself!).

We have no idea when the outflows will cease, and presently we produce more and more each moment and each generation has more crises to solve (or ask God to solve). God maintains He Himself to be desirous of being tested (not tempted), and believed in, and tried out for the “real gold” that “never disappoints.”⁷¹

Would the ultimate of faith be to trust in this process? Particularly, if mimsical analysis above holds, in the One, the Two, and the Three:

1. Lord
2. Force
3. Aether (Heaven)

Note that when the star, Shamash, broke apart what emerged was indeed the 1, then 2, and then the 3 /|\ which became the symbol or “secret name for God” (according to the Arthurian Khumry/Cymru)⁷². So therefore mankind has always pursued the mystery of 1+2=3, including with trigram understanding of the 8 laws (the ‘bagua dharma’⁷³), and multiple three layer systems (such as the US government’s ‘checks and balances’).

The only difference proposed herein, is stricter data evidentiary controls and especially, a hard look at our social and customary assumptions regarding the Diagrammatica that we have inherited, which of course **lacks exact and precise equational expression**.

This isn’t necessarily a flaw in the MIMS philosophy’s opinion; only in STEMM.

Conclusions

The above Diagrammatica is a foundation of mimsical exploration, *not a final solution*. It takes the more concise Figures 1 and 2 and breaks them into logical and experiential parts.

⁷⁰ The “Lawnmower Man” scenario, proposed by S. King as a villainous situation, at least if combined with electrical power...

⁷¹ This is the Faith MIMS

⁷² By the by, if Uranus is the Hades character, then the Tetragrammaton includes the Satanic principle, which has massive implications for both Judeo Christianity and for the facts of the failures (and successes?) of our Zionist World Order presently controlling things... and apparently about to be overthrown by the more powerful Asiatic signals (the Axis).

Moreover, what does this say about the conversion to a 4-dimensional “space time”?

⁷³ https://www.academia.edu/50804995/Bagua_Dharma_Lectures_1_and_2

⁷⁴ Plasma Electromagnetic Cosmology; See: <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>
www.epemcgateway.com

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Unfortunately, at this stage, it is highly subjective despite the strong, self-consistency and numerological adherence. Nevertheless, it shouldn't be easily dismissed, as multiple examples are given which, at the very least, warrant explorations with a liberal but not Critical Theorist's warped perspective. Be honest about egalitarianism, humanism, etc. and be liberal of words, not self-limited and therefore hating of people by hating of words; "misanlogos, misanthropos."

The goal of this philosophy is to leverage MIMS for world, self, and nature improvement. So far only a few axis and doshas are seemingly worth leverage, and most have assumptions in our societies that are (naturally) quite incorrect and potentially hazardous. Hence: world pollution and destruction caused by STEMM, and not improvement, which is what the best MIMS: the Scientific Method, should suggest. Coherence and logic should not render us weak but strong. But it takes courage and honesty to be that strong, and that honest. The Truth is most people would not stand up to Hitler. We have a new Hitler in the works... several... and all of them are strong POS Theory candidates! Many of them have been allowed or told they can be and do whatever they want to others. This is a problem, and it is everyone's problem... including those not even born yet.

It is time to utilize a philosophy that says "no" when necessary in order to say yes to that which is timely, fortunate, karmically beneficial or equanimous, and fated to actually work, instead of toxically pollute the world, the human spirit, and the human soul (by taking advantage of that which is deficient in us, exploiting psycho-biological hacks such as materialism and greed). This is a brave request, made hopefully to brave readers. "Be the Change you want to see in the world."⁷⁵

Not ironically, one of the best mimsical songs ever made, was made by the aforementioned Michael Jackson, perhaps in a moment of grave self-reflection, and prayer. We take it that it is not an anti-MIMS, for it was not the suggestion or song which killed him, but his involvement with toxic medicine - poisons - and with an industry bent on *using people and loving money*. Perhaps his wealth killed him. But it wasn't his love that did so. And in the end, perhaps he was innocent... only those guilty of hiding the Truth could answer that. Without further adieu, "Man in the Mirror":

*I'm gonna make a change
For once in my life
It's gonna feel real good
Gonna make a difference
Gonna make it right
As I, turn up the collar on
My favorite winter coat
This wind is blowin' my mind
I see the kids in the street
With not enough to eat
Who am I, to be blind pretending not to see their needs?
A summer's disregard
A broken bottle top
And a one man's soul
They follow each other on the wind ya know*

⁷⁵ Ghandi

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*'Cause they got nowhere to go
That's why I want you to know
I'm starting with the man in the mirror
I'm asking him to change his ways
And no message could've been any clearer
If they wanna make the world a better place
Take a look at yourself and then make a change
I've been a victim of a selfish kind of love
It's time that I realize
That there are some with no home
Not a nickel to loan
Could it be really me pretending that they're not alone?
A willow deeply scarred
Somebody's broken heart
And a washed out dream (washed out dream)
They follow the pattern of the wind, ya see
'Cause they got no place to be
That's why I'm starting with me
I'm starting with the man in the mirror (oh)
I'm asking him to change his ways (oh)
And no message could've been any clearer
If you wanna make the world a better place
Take a look at yourself and then make a change*

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